

CASE STUDY METHOD FOR EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT RESEARCHES**Gerlie S. Amorin**

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ABSTRACT

Case study is a research approach that is used to generate highly comprehensive and multi-faceted understanding of complex conditions, issues, problems and challenges in scholarly studies. This study explored the significance of Case Study method and the challenges encountered by teachers in administering qualitative studies using case study method. The study used a phenomenological research design in order to determine teachers' experiences in conducting qualitative studies using case study method and their challenges encountered. It was participated by 100 randomly selected teachers among selected public elementary schools in the Philippines. The study found out that teachers' significantly use case study method in conducting educational researches where they value its contextual analysis structure, wider exploration of complex issues and investigative aspects. Further, the study emphasized that teachers were extremely challenged in doing case study researches as they experienced that using Case Study method posed time constraints and difficulty in accessing the participants. Hence, the study recommended that teachers should develop a more relevant studies which would fit the use case study design. Also, the study recommends that teachers should be careful and keen in the proper implementation of case study processes and procedures. Thus, the study proposed a model which may help teachers to deepen their understanding and competence in applying case study method on educational management researches.

Keywords:

case study, method, contextual analysis, structure, exploration, complex, investigative, aspects, proposed model

INTRODUCTION

Educational management and supervision is a critical dimension for the implementation of sound governance among academic institutions. It involves the internal and external governance which highlight the schools' affairs, operations and other undertakings which are represented by school heads as leaders of the schools as institutions and managers whose functions and responsibilities include proper directions for the continued development of the schools. There are founded principles in educational management and supervision that have been structured for more than decades. In this regard, introduction of different theories, laws, principles and concepts in educational leadership, management and supervision are instituted based on the resurfacing changes in the educational landscape dependent on the country's educational policies and systems. With long lines of educational management theories, there are fundamental areas by which school leaders rely on. The scientific administration of scholarly studies help school heads consistently describe, examine and assess the prevailing conditions of the schools, the leadership and management processes, styles, systems among others. As such, administration of research studies is the foremost concern of all members of academic communities specially those professionals who are advocating the continued innovation and development within the systems of

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educational management and supervision. Research as one of the pillars in higher education, is treated as an important mechanism to consistently validate the conditions and examine the circumstances which schools and its personnel experience. Fundamentally, research is a systematized process which aims to establish facts and reach new conclusions that are vital in the development of individuals, institutions and other entities concerned under the conduct of such. In this line, scholars are advancing their interests in the development knowledge construct that can help the system, institutions and their colleagues in improving certain dimensions as emphasized on specific context and nature of their research undertaking. Following this, the Philippine educational system promotes the professional development among teachers. Accordingly, one of the primary methods of acquiring professional development is the completion of teachers' graduate studies whereas, here they are expected to develop scholarly studies that would provide substantial impact to their institutions. Along this line, teachers are commonly anxious in doing or developing research studies because of their intricacies. The process, methods and technical aspect of writing research undertaking are common concerns of teachers why they tend to avoid conducting research studies. But because of their desire to reach maximum professional development, they are obligated to conduct such studies relative to their discipline. On one hand, they are also tasked to perform classroom-based action research that primarily intends to resolve instructional deficiencies they encountered in an actual teaching and learning process.

Apparently, one of the common research methods widely used by teachers in the field is descriptive quantitative research design. The researchers observed that most of their colleagues selected research topics that are appropriate for such design. In addition, they also observed that most of their colleagues pursue instructional-based researches even they are studying educational management and supervision discipline under their graduate studies. With this, the researchers observed that there may be a strong gap between the appropriateness of the topic to the discipline or area of expertise being pursued under the graduate program. In this line, the researchers plunged their interest to comprehensively explore if public school teachers do use or employ case study design as a chosen research design in conducting their research studies whether under institutional research undertaking or as part of their requirement in graduate studies. Case study methodology has long been a contested terrain in social sciences research which is characterized by varying and most seldom, opposing approaches (Yazan, 2015). Further, case study is an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context specially when the boundaries between the object of the study and contest are not clearly evident (Ebneyamini & Moghadam, 2018). A number of international journal articles were taken as corpus of the study which utilized varieties of methods such as grounded theory and case study (Atmowardoyo, 2018). In educational policy research, linking specific practices to specific outcomes was an important goal hence, qualitative comparative using case study design had the potential to be of use to educational researches (Bingham 2019).

In view of the foregoing conditions observed by the researchers and the knowledge gaps extracted on the previous studies cited, this study explored the significance of Case Study method and the challenges encountered by teachers in administering qualitative studies using Case Study method. Hence, the study was significant as findings herein could be used for the development of localized or school-based program intervention emphasizing the development of teachers' research competence in using Case Study method as they administer educational management and supervision related studies.

OBJECTIVES

This study explored the significance of Case Study method and the challenges encountered by teachers in administering qualitative studies using case study method. The study used a phenomenological research design in order to determine teachers' experiences in conducting qualitative studies using case study method and their challenges encountered.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed phenomenological research design in order to explore the significance of Case Study method and the challenges encountered by teachers in administering qualitative studies using Case Study method. The study used developed guide questions for Focus Group Discussion (FGD). Inductive method was used in the construction of guide questions. Apparently, the researchers sought the expertise of graduate school

professors to validate the developed guide questions. After the validation process, the researchers complied with the suggestions and recommendations of expert-validators. The study used simple random sampling to select the participation of public elementary school teachers in the Philippines. The researchers posted on their social media account a call for participation for this study. Hence, such posting was made publicly and was deleted on their personal social media account upon reaching the intended sample size of the study. Further, when the participants have already been enlisted, the researchers sent a formal letter of invitation through their personal social media accounts and email addresses. Once they have expressed their deliberate participation, the researchers conducted an online short orientation before the participants where the researchers discussed the context, nature, scope and objectives of the study. Thereafter, when time availability of the participants has been finalized and fixed, the researchers conducted a Focus Group Discussion where participants were scheduled on their given dates. In addition, the researchers provided ten (10) to fifteen (15) minutes to complete the Focus Group Discussion. The responses were recorded in verbatim format where the researchers prepared a Table of Qualitative Responses (TQR) then they were able to extract the major themes and subthemes of the study. In this regard, the data analysis technique used by the researchers was thematic analysis. On one hand, since this study employed qualitative method specifically phenomenological research design, they adhered to the highest ethical standards in developing a qualitative research study through provision of formal invitation letters, informed consent and short orientations made through online channel. Also, the researchers stored the gathered qualitative data on their personal devices such as laptop and mobile phones. Hence, gathered data were permanently deleted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Case study method is a systematic approach under the qualitative method in research where the intent and nature of the study is to explore different conditions, experiences and situations which individuals encountered under the given context. Case study method is also used to formulate more in-depth analysis on the conditions and experiences as well as the phenomena surrounding the topical subject of a research study. In this paper, the significance of Case Study was explored and the challenges which teachers faced in administering such method under qualitative studies. It is within the line of educational researches, several conditions and situations confront teachers that may or may not directly impact their teaching performance. Significance of this study was vested on the comprehensive exploration on how Case study method was used and how it implicated public elementary school teachers' when doing qualitative studies parallel to their teaching functions, roles and performance. Also, the study explored the challenges they encountered in using Case Study method in administering education-related researches under the principles of qualitative method in research.

1. **Use of Case Study Method in Conducting Educational Management Researches.** Teachers used Case Study method because of its systematized structure enabling them to make a deep exploration and scrutiny on the *contextual structure* of the conditions and responses expressed by their participants in doing educational researches. It showed that one of the primordial strengths of Case Study method in conducting educational management researches was its contextual analysis structure whereas teachers as they expressed, were able to significantly present the cultural, social, pedagogical, institutional and other factors surrounding the conditions, problems or gaps they have observed. In this line, they were also able to formulate a more profound and highly comprehensive discussion of results as they conduct their formulated educational researches. The findings also showed that teachers significantly used Case Study method because they could also relate with the diverse experiences and situations that were experienced by their participants. Apparently, the findings also underscored that teachers used Case Study method on the basis that they could feel that their administered educational researches were more impactful and applicable to the relevant practices of their participants who were also teachers. On *wider exploration of complex issues*. The findings showed that teachers significantly used Case Study method because they could be able to present multifaceted issues. In addition, teachers employed Case Study method because it could allow them to explore diverse issues from various angles, points of views and perceptions of diverse reach of participants as they administered their educational researches. In other words, teachers expressed that Case Study was significant because they could be able to deduce all important factors, conditions, situations and experiences that their participants encountered. Another significance on the use of Case Study method as shared by teachers, here, they could be able to gather rich data through highly systematized process such as interviews, observations

and document analyses. *On investigative aspects*, results showed that teachers significantly employed Case Study method because they would want to impose a deeper method of inquiry in investigating certain conditions which their educational researches contained or being contextualized. Teachers also expressed according from the findings, that they were highly engaged in the research process because of the subjectivity but systematic forms of data gathering process attached to Case Study method. The findings also implied that teachers used Case Study method because their skills and competence in conducting educational researches was developed. Succinctly, when they administered interviews, observations, discussions and document analysis, their competence and diligence in developing their educational researches has been developed and potentially, implicated critical thinking and problem solving skills. Results of the study supported the study of Wyatt (2022) which concluded that Case study research has played a very important role in applied linguistics and education since the method and form of Case Study research reflected the actual experiences, situations and cases where participants really subjected to. Similar study showed that cases were normally studied in depth in order to provide an understanding of individuals experiences. The study implicated that there should be a strong policy in using Case Study method where teachers as researchers in their field, could benefit from it. Part of such policy are training programs, workshops and support to be provided for the teachers in order to strengthened their research skills in using Case Study method in developing and conducting educational researches.

2. **Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Using Case Study Method in Administering Qualitative Studies.** As teachers significantly used Case Study method, there were several challenges they encountered which caused them to experience difficulty in developing qualitative studies in the field of education. *On time constraints*, the findings showed that teachers experienced that conducting educational researches with use of Case Study method required significant amount of time for data collection, analysis and discussion and interpretation. The findings revealed that teachers often have limited time due to their teaching responsibilities and other designated tasks in the school that posed difficulty to dedicate an adequate amount of time to research and complete their qualitative research work. Apparently, under time constraints, findings showed that teachers struggled to balance their research activities with their instructional duties and responsibilities. Meanwhile, *on the difficulty in accessing the participants*, it showed that teachers found it difficult to gain access to their selected participants because of the prevailing data privacy provisions. Also, under this theme, the study found out that teachers found it challenging to harmonize their participants' work schedule and the research time frame. In this line, availability in scheduling interviews and focus groups were challenging. Hence, the study also found that teachers as researchers using Case Study method often confronted with conflicting schedules that hampered them to facilitate the processes of the Case Study research. Results of the study were supported by the study of Paparini et al. (2020) which argued that Case study research was denigrated as poor evidence due to underutilized resources. Similar study also showed that researchers using Case Study research were challenged on the time in conducting their interviews, focus groups discussions, observations and document analyses.
3. **Proposed Model in Developing Teachers' Competence in Applying Case Study Method in Educational Management Researches** This study proposed a model that may help teachers develop their competence in applying Case Study Method in Educational Management researches. The researchers crafted CASE (Collaborative, Applied, Sequential and Evaluative) model. This model emphasizes the use of **collaboration** where teachers could seek support from groups or colleagues who possess expertise in writing researches using Case Study method. It could be perfected through the use of mentorship programs and tutorial sessions. Also, the model underscored **applied** training workshops whereas teachers would be provided with relevant lectures and interactive activities that practically apply their knowledge and learned concepts in doing case study researches. Also, the model emphasized sequential aspect as it contained that teachers should be provided with series of trainings, mentorship program and research enhancement activities that should not be made only once for every school year. Lastly, the model introduced evaluative aspect whereas the school heads and research focal persons should create precise metrics to regularly evaluate teachers' research writing competence.

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CONCLUSION

Case study was a recognized and widely used research method in educational management researches that delve deeper on the situations, conditions and experiences encountered by teachers, school heads and administrators. Teachers significantly used Case Study method in developing and completing their educational management researches as the same contained comprehensive process and procedures on contextual analysis structure aspect, profounded wider exploration of complex issues and investigative aspects. However, while teachers significantly used Case Study method in doing educational management researches, they experienced time constraints and difficulty in accessing the participants. Hence, CASE model was proposed as an output of this study.

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